

Assessment and assessment as a means of motivation for learning a foreign language

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Annotation. The importance of control at different stages of learning a foreign language is emphasized. The need for objective assessment and marking during learning is substantiated, 13 since there is a close relationship between assessment and the formation, maintenance and strengthening of motivation in mastering a foreign language. It is concluded that an objective, comprehensive assessment is an important motivating stimulus for a student and an effective tool in a teacher's arsenal.

Key words: control, assessment, marking, motivation, maintenance and strengthening.

The need to improve various types of control for a reliable and objective assessment of the results achieved by students is one of the most discussed topics in pedagogy, especially when teaching a foreign language. Currently, due to fierce competition in the labor market, the need for highly qualified specialists who are able to communicate in a foreign language is steadily increasing. However, we live not only to solve economic problems. Educational tasks are no less important.

Nowadays, students have many opportunities to travel for exchange studies and receive education at educational institutions in different countries. It is natural that such an important question of assessment arises here, how high quality is the preparation of students in terms of language.

The problem of assessment was and is one of the most important components of the educational process at all stages of teaching a foreign language. With the help of control and evaluation, a number of different functions are carried out teaching, predicting, diagnosing, and developing and, of course, educational.

Without a doubt, the further desire to continue studying and, as a consequence, the entire learning outcome depends on how well control and assessment is

organized. To put it differently, assessment is one of the very significant means of motivating students when learning a foreign language at all stages of learning. If we compare the meaning of the concepts: “assessment” and “mark”, then it becomes obvious that they are not identical. The mark is a point indicator that is established by state standards in order to indicate the degree of knowledge of each specific student.

An assessment can be called a verbal (verbal) description of the results, diligence, aspirations, efforts on the part of the student; often the assessment is of a detailed nature. The mark should follow from the assessment, but not vice versa. Giving a mark should be a natural result of the process of monitoring and assessing students’ skills. The mark is most often a quantitative characteristic, which is expressed by the total amount of points, summed up from the assessments of each of the criteria of the controlled skill. Here we can highlight several problems that a teacher may encounter: - how to create a diagram that would clearly reflect the assessment; – how to remain fair when assessing students; – how to assess students’ skills in various types of speech activity; – how to find an individual approach to a student; – how to expand the vector of assessment from a focus on external control to improving learning achievements (learning outcomes), as well as increasing the interest (motivation) of students in learning a foreign language. If we follow the meaning of such terms as “control”, “check”, “assessment” in domestic didactics, we will find that they are often used as synonyms and complement each other. With regard to testing learning outcomes or control, these terms are usually considered as pedagogical diagnostics. Assessment in didactics usually refers to the process of comparing the level that students managed to achieve with the standard concepts described in the curriculum. Regarding the process itself, the assessment of knowledge, skills and abilities is carried out during control or verification of the latter. The conventionally accepted reflection of the assessment is a mark, which is usually expressed in points. The process of identifying and comparing, at one or another stage of learning, the results of educational activities with the requirements specified by curricula, and learning goals. Expressed in the form of a mark (in points) or a verbal value judgment by the teacher. Testing and evaluation include determining the goals and objectives of training, requirements for learning outcomes at each stage of the educational process; selection of test tasks, examples and method of expressing test results. All components of verification and assessment are

interrelated and must be considered as a unity.” For Motivation is necessary for the normal implementation of any human activity. It is of particular importance for cognition, and in the process of teaching a foreign language at each of the individual stages its role is very large. Psychologists traditionally distinguish between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation. When learning a foreign language, external motivation is based on the importance and international recognition of the English language, increasing competitiveness in the labor market, etc. I. A. Zimnyaya connects internal motivation with the effectiveness of educational activities, with the satisfaction of the need to improve performance results. E. Deacy, R. Ryan, R. Frankin write in their work about internal motivation as the desire to find something new for the application and further development of one’s own abilities, for research and learning.

Research behavior, in their opinion, implies a person’s subjective assessment of his skills in relation to solving the tasks or situations facing him. Psychology has not yet come to a consensus in understanding what motivation essentially is and what its role is in regulating human behavior.

If there is no success, this will inevitably lead to the fading of its results, it should help the teacher select the most effective techniques and means of teaching that could stimulate the development of students, their further motivation, and which, in turn, will negatively affect educational activities . On the other hand, the teacher must focus on the student’s internal motivation, his current tasks and needs; develop interest in a foreign language.

The most important question that every teacher needs to find an answer to at the stage of knowledge control, regardless of what subject he teaches, including foreign language teachers, is “How to objectively and impartially evaluate a student without belittling his human dignity, How can we make assessment not only educational and educational, but also, to a large extent, a motivating factor?”

When working with students, it is necessary to use all types of control for visual and objective assessment and marking: 1. Introductory, which allows you to assess the level of knowledge of students, general erudition. To do this, you can use testing, conversation, questioning, observation. 2. Current, which allows you to assess the degree of mastery of educational material on a specific topic, educational unit, for which diagnostic tasks are well suited, namely: surveys, tasks and practical work, various types of testing. 3. Corrective, allowing to identify and eliminate gaps

and shortcomings. To do this, we can offer the use of repeated tests, as well as individual consultations, allowing for an individual approach to the student. 4. Final, which makes it possible to assess the degree of completion of the assigned tasks. Here, different types of reading, translation, annotation, testing and other types of tasks are used to assess various aspects.

In foreign language classes, students' knowledge can be assessed through frontal and individual work. With a frontal survey, in a short period of time it is possible to assess the state of knowledge of all students in each group. An individual oral survey allows you to assess the correctness of the answer in terms of content, its consistency, independence of judgment, the logic of constructing a statement, and the speech culture of each student. This form is used for current and thematic accounting. Oral questioning is carried out at every lesson; correct assessment of students' knowledge plays an important role here. Testing in written form allows you to assess the knowledge of a large number of students simultaneously in a short time. Students' written work is carried out in the form of control, verification and independent work, tests. Increasingly, we began to use tests to test knowledge. The test allows you to quickly and relatively simply, under equal conditions for all subjects, make an assessment. At the same time, it is very important not to stop only at assigning points for the completed test, but to analyze its results, giving a detailed assessment of the result. A test or exam is conducted to determine the achievement of the final learning outcomes on a specific topic by each student. At this stage, you should also not limit yourself to just setting a point mark. This stage is very important in terms of motivation and requires special attention from the teacher. If we talk specifically about the process of teaching foreign languages within a university, we can conclude that a foreign language, being one of the few humanitarian disciplines in the educational cycle, has all the capabilities to solve not only educational, but also a whole range of educational tasks in the formation of personality future professionals.

The assessment, in turn, must be effective and comprehensive. It should be based on objective indicators, allow the process of determining the final grade to be formalized, provide feedback, and the system should also be flexible enough. All this will stimulate motivation to learn a foreign language, which, in turn, will improve the quality of specialist training.

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